

Proof of the Pythagorean theorem using coordinate and functions

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1 Abstract

The Pythagorean theorem can be proven by defining coordinates and functions and finding their areas.

2 Introduction

Generally, the Pythagorean theorem is often proven using geometrical properties such as similarity and congruence. This time, we defined coordinates and functions and proved the Pythagorean theorem.

The Pythagorean theorem is usually used to find the distance c between coordinates (a, b) and the origin. However, I wanted to determine the coordinates (a, b) and complete the proof from there.

Derivation of coordinates and functions

First, set the x - y coordinates and determine one point, as shown in Figure 1. Let the coordinates at this time be $A(a,b)$.

Let the equation of the straight line passing through point A and the origin be $OA : y=\alpha x$. This straight line is called OA . α is a proportionality constant. At this time, let c be the distance between point A and the origin .

$$A(c \cdot \cos \beta, c \cdot \sin \beta) = A(a, b)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{b}{a} \quad (0 < \alpha < \infty)$$

$$0 < \beta < \frac{\pi}{2}$$

Let β be the angle between the x -axis and OA , and let C be the point that is perpendicular to OA and has length c . The coordinates of C can be expressed as follows using angle β .

$$C(c \cdot \cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - \beta), -c \cdot \sin(\frac{\pi}{2} - \beta)) = C(c \cdot \sin \beta, -c \cdot \cos \beta) = C(b, -a)$$

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Figure 1: A and angle β

Let OC be the straight line passing through origin O and point C.
 Find the equation of straight line BC. Let D be the intercept. BC By passing through point C, we can find D.

Figure 2: OA and OC and AB and BC

$$BC : y = \alpha x + D = \alpha x - \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{a}$$

$$D(0, -\frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{a})$$

Find the equation of line AB. Let E be the intercept. By passing through A, we can find E.

$$AB : y = -\frac{1}{\alpha} x + E = -\frac{1}{\alpha} x + \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{b}$$

$$E(0, \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{b})$$

Find the intersection B of AB and BC.

$$B(a + b, b - a)$$

Find the area of the square consisting of OA, AB, OB, BC. This is called OABC, and the area is c^2 .

3 Proof using integral

These can also be derived by integral. If it is determined by integration, the range of integration changes depending on whether B is above or below the y-axis.

Figure 3: Integral range

$$OAF = \int_0^a \alpha x dx = \frac{1}{2} \alpha a^2 = \frac{1}{2} ab$$

$$OCG = - \int_0^b -\frac{1}{\alpha} x dx = \frac{1}{2} ab$$

$$AFIB = \int_a^{a+b} \left(-\frac{1}{\alpha} x + \frac{a^2 + b^2}{b} \right) dx = \frac{-ab + 2b^2}{2}$$

$$HIB = \int_b^{a+b} \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{b} \left(\alpha x - \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a} \right) dx = \frac{ab^2 - 2a^2b + a^3}{2b}$$

$$CGH = - \int_b^{a+b} \frac{(a^2 + b^2)}{b} \left(\alpha x - \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a} \right) dx = \frac{a^3}{2b}$$

If one side of a square is c , the area of the square can be expressed using coordinates (a, b) . From the above, the following is derived.

$$c^2 = OABC = OAB + OCG + GCH + AFIB - HIB = a^2 + b^2$$

4 Proof using coordinate

OABC is triangle BDE minus triangles OCD and OAE.

$$BDE = \frac{(a+b)}{2} \left(\frac{a^2+b^2}{b} + \frac{a^2+b^2}{a} \right)$$

$$OAE = \frac{a}{2} \frac{a^2+b^2}{b}$$

$$OCD = \frac{b}{2} \frac{a^2+b^2}{a}$$

$$OABC = BDE - OAE - OCD$$

Substitute the above formula into this and calculate.

$$OABC = BDE - OAE - OCD = a^2 + b^2$$

$$OABC = c^2$$

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2$$

5 Case of second quadrant

When β is small, B belongs to the second quadrant. In this case too, the same formula can be obtained by performing the same calculations as above.